

ON THE STIFFNESS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATE WITH DELAMINATIONS FOR ANALYTICAL MODEL OF LOW VELOCITY IMPACT

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Keywords: Composite laminate, Low velocity impact, Delamination, Bending stiffness, Analytical model

ABSTRACT

A mathematical model for stiffness of composite laminate with delaminations was presented. Plate was divided into a delaminated portion of central disk and an undamaged portion of annulus plate. Bending theory and classical lamination theory were used to obtain the displacement of the plate to compute the stiffness. A FE model was established to validate the analytical model. Comparison with FE simulation and experiment test results showed good agreement of the stiffness reduction and the prediction of contact force history.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their excellent performance of strength, light weight and resistance to corrosion, polymer matrix composite laminates are extensively used in the aircraft structures and automotive industries. But poor damage resistance under transverse impact such as dropping of tools makes them susceptible to impact damage like matrix crack, delamination etc. The invisible damage of delamination can occur in mild impacts and may decrease the residual strength of material.

Energy-balance model and spring-mass model are two types of simple analytical models proposed to describe the problem of low-velocity impact on composite laminates. Different with energy-balance model, spring-mass model can not only estimate the impact force but also the history of force or displacement throughout the impact. Abrate[1] studied four forms of spring-mass models and presented an approach for selecting an appropriate model for a particular case. Olsson[2] presented a modified version of model to predict delamination initiation and growth during impact on plates with large deflection, indentation and shearing. Li Shizhe[3] proposed a method based on spring-mass model for impacting delamination response of composite laminates. Yu Zhefeng[4] modeled the permanent indentation of impact with the closed nonlinear spring-mass model and comparison showed good performance of the analytical model with experimental results. Ning Baojun[5] reduced the flexural rigidity of the spring-mass model according to C-scan results to obtain the contact load and energy absorption histories after the delamination initiation.

In the present paper, an analytical model is established for composite laminates with delamination under low velocity impact and a FE model is constructed to support the fidelity of the analytical model.

The results of single spring-mass model corresponds well with FE data and result from impact experiment of 10J.

2 STIFFNESS WITH DELIMINATION

1.1 Spring-mass model

Low velocity impact of composite laminate is an important issue in the structural engineering. The impact can be simulated with single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) or two-degree-of freedom (TDOF) spring-mass model. The nonlinear SDOF model is shown as Fig. 1, and the governing equation is written as[1]:

$$m\ddot{x} + K_{bs}x + K_m x^3 = 0 \quad (1)$$

where K_{bs} is the stiffness associated to the bending stiffness of the plate and the shearing stiffness. Sometimes for thin plate K_s is negligible, so K_{bs} can be written as K_b . The above model is effective in simulating the response of the impact point if there is no delamination occurs. While it is meaningful to predict the response after the presence of delamination damage, for example the energy absorption history after the delamination initiation. This paper proposed an analytical method to calculate the stiffness associated to the bending stiffness of the plate with a delamination region.

Figure 1: The SDOF model of impact on composite laminates

1.2 Overall stiffness

The stiffness associated the flexural rigidity is evaluated by dividing the composite laminates into a central delaminated region surrounded by an undamaged region (Fig. 2). The deflection at center where F exerted should be gained in order to calculate the effective stiffness of this point. The deflection at the center is determined by separately finding the solution of two cases[6]: a central disk with concentrated load F along with a distributed edge moment M_a and a fixed outer edge (Fig. 3(b)), and an annulus plate with load $Q_a = F/2\pi r_d$ and moment M_a applied at the inner boundary(Fig. 3(c)). Both deflection of the two region can be calculated with analytical model, when given M_a . The slope, $\partial w/\partial r$, on the boundary of the two regions is equal to each other, which is the compatible condition in solving M_a .

Figure 2: Schematic of delamination region in the laminated plate: (a) global deflection and (b) deflection detail in the delaminated region.

Figure 3: Balance of the delaminated region and the undamaged region

For the simply supported central disk of radius r under concentrated load F , the transverse displacement w can be written as

$$w = C_1 \ln r + C_2 r^2 \ln r + C_3 r^2 + C_4$$

$$= \{\ln r, r^2 \ln r, r^2, 1\} \{C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4\}^T \quad (2)$$

The boundary conditions are

$$w = 0 \quad \text{on } r = 0$$

C_1 then can be worked out to be zero, and the derivative of w with respect of r can be obtained as following

$$\frac{dw}{dr} = 2C_2 r \ln r + C_2 r + 2C_3 r$$

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{dw}{dr} = 2C_2 \ln r + C_2 + 2C_3 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d^2 w}{dr^2} = 2C_2 \ln r + 3C_2 + 2C_3$$

Using the definition for equivalent bending rigidity D in [1], the moment M_r and shearing force Q_r of the plate are

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_r &= -D\left(\frac{d^2w}{dr^2} + \frac{\mu}{r} \frac{dw}{dr}\right) \\
 &= -D[2(1+\mu)C_2 \ln r + (3+\mu)C_2 + 2(1+\mu)C_3] \\
 Q_r &= -D \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{d^2w}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{dw}{dr}\right) \\
 &= -D \frac{4C_2}{r}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Concentrated load F is actually conducted on a small region which can be written as $\frac{F}{2\pi c}$ (c is rather small), so C_2 is given by $\frac{F}{8\pi D}$ derived from Eq. (5)

$$D \frac{4C_2}{c} = \frac{F}{2\pi c} \tag{5}$$

Substituting $C_1 = 0$, $C_2 = \frac{P}{8\pi D}$ into Eq. (2), and w is expressed as

$$w = \frac{Fr^2}{8\pi D} \ln r + C_3 r^2 + C_4 \tag{6}$$

At outer edge $r = a$, the boundary conditions are

$$w_{r=a} = 0 \quad (M_r)_{r=a} = -M_a$$

Where the first equation in Eq. (3) and Eq. (6) are written as

$$\frac{Fa^2}{8\pi D} \ln a + C_3 a^2 + C_4 = 0 \tag{7}$$

$$-D[2C_2(1+\mu) \ln a + (3+\mu)C_2 + 2(1+\mu)C_3] = M_a \tag{8}$$

Rewrite in the form of matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} a^2 & 1 \\ -2D & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} C_3 \\ C_4 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\frac{Fa^2}{8\pi D} \ln a \\ \frac{M_a}{D(1+\mu)} + \frac{F}{8\pi D} \frac{[2(1+\mu) \ln a + 3 + \mu]}{1+\mu} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{9}$$

For the simply supported annulus plate with distributed load Q_a and moment M_a at the inner boundary, the transverse displacement w can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 w &= C_5 \ln r + C_6 r^2 \ln r + C_7 r^2 + C_8 \\
 &= \{\ln r, r^2 \ln r, r^2, 1\} \{C_5, C_6, C_7, C_8\}^T
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Same as the central disk, the moment and shearing force of the annulus plate are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dw}{dr} &= C_5 \frac{1}{r} + 2C_6 r \ln r + C_6 r + 2C_7 r \\ \frac{1}{r} \frac{dw}{dr} &= C_5 \frac{1}{r^2} + 2C_6 \ln r + C_6 + 2C_7 \\ \frac{d^2w}{dr^2} &= -C_5 \frac{1}{r^2} + 2C_6 \ln r + 3C_6 + 2C_7\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned}M_r &= -D \left(\frac{d^2w}{dr^2} + \frac{\mu}{r} \frac{dw}{dr} \right) \\ &= -D \left[-C_5(1-\mu) \frac{1}{r^2} + 2C_6(1+\mu) \ln r + C_6(3+\mu) + 2C_7(1+\mu) \right] \\ Q_r &= -D \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{dw}{dr} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{dw}{dr} \right) \\ &= -D \frac{4C_6}{r}\end{aligned}\quad (12)$$

The boundary conditions at $r = b$ and $r = a$ are

$$w_{r=b} = 0 \quad (M_r)_{r=b} = 0, \quad (Q_r)_{r=a} = -Q_a \quad (M_r)_{r=a} = -M_a$$

So we get an equation group and write it in matrix form

$$\begin{bmatrix} \ln b & b^2 \ln b & b^2 & 1 \\ -\frac{(1-\mu)}{b^2} & 2(1+\mu) \ln b + 3 + \mu & 2(1+\mu) & 0 \\ D \frac{(1-\mu)}{b^2} & -D[2(1+\mu) \ln b + 3 + \mu] & -2D(1+\mu) & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{4D}{a} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} C_5 \\ C_6 \\ C_7 \\ C_8 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -M_a \\ -Q_a \end{Bmatrix}\quad (13)$$

1.3 Load and displacement of the delaminated region

According to [7][8], overall moment, in-plane tensile and shear force of multiply laminated area are

$$\begin{aligned}Q_a &= \sum_{k=1}^N Q_{dk} \\ M_a &= \sum_{k=1}^N (M_{dk} + z_k N_{rdk}) \\ N_a &= \sum_{k=1}^N N_{rdk} \\ N_{rdk} &= N_{\theta k} = -\frac{E_k h_k}{1-\nu_k} \frac{z_k}{a} \dot{w}(a)\end{aligned}\quad (14)$$

Where N_a is the in-plane resultant stress of whole central plate at $r = a$, M_{dk} , N_{rdk} , h_k are the moments, in-plane stresses and thickness of each delaminated portion. z_k is the distance of the middle surface of k^{th} delaminated portion from the mid-plane of the whole plate, and E_k the mean flexural modulus using

compliance matrix components S_{11} and S_{22} [9], ν_k the equivalent Poisson's ratio of each delaminated portion.

As the second equation in Eq. (15) shows, the moment M_a which through whole damage region at the delamination front are of contribution of moment M_{dk} in each delaminated ply and the resulting moment caused by the in-plane resulting stress N_{rdk} .

$$\sum_{k=1}^N M_{dk} = M_a - \sum_{k=1}^N z_k N_{rdk} \quad (15)$$

M_{dk} is relative to the effective bending stiffness D_k of the k^{th} delaminated portion. As for M_a , an arbitrary initial value is used for the estimation of the slope $\partial w / \partial r$ on the boundary of the two regions. Because of the assumption of classical lamination theory, transverse displacement through thickness of each ply are of the same, a certain ply's displacement represents whole plate's motion.

The bending rigidity of the region with N delaminated sub-laminates (Fig. 2(b)), D_n , is computed using

$$D_n = \sum_{k=1}^N D_k \quad (16)$$

Actually, the aforementioned moment M_{dk} is proportional to the ratio of D_k / D_n . Hence $M_{dk} = M_a D_k / D_n$, $Q_{dk} = Q_a D_k / D_n$.

For a delaminated plate having a radius of 50mm with delamination region in equivalent radius of 20mm, the delamination case described as "2-6" means an 8-ply composite laminates plate delaminated into two sub-laminates in the central disk region. One contains two plies and another has six. And in case "2-3-3", sure it is delaminated into three sub-laminates and each has two, three and three plies, separately. The laminate material properties used are as shown in Table. 1.

Engineering constant	Identification	Unit
E_{11}	120	[GPa]
$E_{22} = E_{33}$	7.80	[GPa]
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.28	—
ν_{23}	0.36	—
$G_{12} = G_{13}$	6.21	[GPa]
G_{23}	3.45	[GPa]

Table 1: Material propertioes

Given an initial value of M_a , the deflection slope for case "2-3-3" on the boundary of the central delamination area and the annulus plate is computed, respectively. Then M_a is manually searched when the two slopes are approximated enough, as shown in Fig. 4. The superposition of deflection under concentrated load of 1000N of the two regions is shown in Fig. 5, where the value at the plate center is used to compute the stiffness together with exerted load F .

Figure 4. The slope of deflection of the two regions for case “2-3-3”

Figure 5. The superposition of the deflection of the two regions for case “2-3-3”

3 NUMERICAL VALIDATION

3.1 Modeling method

A finite element (FE) model with an 8-ply composite laminates along with a semi-spherical analytical rigid body indenter (Fig. 6) is developed to validate the analytical model using the commercial ABAQUS/ Standard code, for that the low velocity impact scenario is quasi-static. Solid element was used to create the 8 laminate plies. The laminates plate has a thickness of 2.3mm, diameter of 100mm, and the ply mechanical properties are listed in Table. 1. As above. Each ply of the laminates is modeled via offsetting a base 3D shell layer into a certain length where the offset length equals to thickness of a

single ply. “Hard” penalty contact was defined between the indenter and the top surface of the composite plate while just penalty contact was defined between adjacent central disk layers without normal behavior. Friction coefficient is set to 0.15 and 0.1, separately.

Figure 6. Finite element model of composite plate with delamination

The cohesive element layers are also created between each laminate plies sharing the nodes with upper and lower laminate layers. The model laminate is partitioned into two parts: a central disk with diameter of 40 mm where cohesive elements were deleted representing the delaminated region, and a fixed outer edge annulus plate to represent the undamaged region with cohesive element preserved (Fig. 7). Fig. 8 shows the result of deflection near the contact area for delamination case “2-3-3”, which delaminated into three sub-laminates and each sub-laminate has two, three and three plies. The 2nd, 5th and 7th cohesive layers are with central element deleted, and the other cohesive layers are complete, three obvious separations are observed between plies.

Figure 7. Cohesive element layer for plies with delamination

Figure 8: The deformation of delamination region with “2-3-3” mode

3.2 Numerical and analytical results

Several delamination cases are simulated here in Table. 2. The relationship between the load and displacement of the indenter complies with Eq. (1). First use least square method to fit the force-displacement curve from result of no delamination case to calculate k_b and k_m . Then in fitting for the other cases, k_m is excluded using the k_m obtained from no delamination case, whose value is 18.48 N/mm³ which the analytical value of k_m for SM boundary is 21.4 N/mm³[10], showing good accuracy for the FE model. The values of k_b for different delamination case scenario are listed in Tabel. 2, where good agreement on the stiffness and stiffness reduction is achieved.

Delamination Case	Stiffness by FEM (N/mm)	Stiffness by analytical model (N/mm)	Error of stiffness (%)	Stiffness reduction by FEM (%)	Stiffness reduction by analytical model (%)	Error stiffness reduction (%)
No delamination	379.90	372.72	-1.89	--	--	--
1-7	375.90	343.38	-8.65	98.94	92.13	-6.88
2-6	337.80	319.07	-5.54	88.92	85.61	-3.72
3-5	303.40	318.13	4.85	79.86	85.35	6.87
4-4	293.10	327.02	12.30	77.15	87.74	13.73
1-3-4	278.70	273.22	1.97	73.36	73.30	0.08
2-2-4	263.40	260.59	-1.07	69.33	69.92	0.85
2-3-3	242.90	233.37	-3.92	63.94	62.61	-2.08
1-2-2-3	229.90	209.67	-8.79	60.52	56.25	-7.05

Table 2: Comparison of the results

The dropping weight impact test was conducted with CEAST-9350 tester of INSTRON company.

Test specimen had a size of 150 mm×100 mm and 2.2 mm thick with a $[(0\ 45\ 90\ -45)_s]_s$ layup. The delaminations were detected using ultrasonic C-scan after the test for their locations and sizes which were shown in Fig. 9, and a “2-5-3-6” delamination case was observed. The reduction of stiffness was then determined to be 45%. The contact force is simulated with SDOF model[3] and was compared with the experimental result (Fig. 10). So it is verified that the proposed method is good in predicting the stiffness and its reduction in the analytical model on the low velocity impact of composite laminate.

Figure 9: The ultrasonic C-scan image

Figure 10: Comparison of contact force in the impact with energy of 10J

4 CONCLUSION

This article presented an analytical model used for the stiffness and reduction of the stiffness for composite laminates with delamination damage. Examples of stiffness results demonstrated that this procedure provides accurate prediction of the reduction of bending stiffness k_b . SDOF spring-mass model are used to calculate the reactive force and duration associated with low-velocity impact on composite laminates. Comparison with drop weight test result showed good agreement of the analytical SDOF prediction of the contact force history.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author thanks the Natural Science Foundation of China for the support provided (Grant No. 11372192).

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